

Cropping systems

Intraspecies intercropping of rice

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The effect of growing improved rice varieties of different growth durations as sole crops (Table 1) or of intercropping two varieties in alternate rows was measured. Experimental varieties were CRM13, IET2683, IET1444, IR579, IR36, and IR42. Days to maturity were from 74 to 142 days in the wet season and from 100 to 164 days in the dry.

Row spacing was 20 cm, plant spacing was 10 cm.

The total intercrop yield increased linearly with differences in maturity of the intercropped varieties. The combination of IET2683 and IR42 gave the maximum grain yield (Table 2). The combined intercrop yield was greater than the sole crop yield for both varieties.

The IET2683 and IR42 intercrop also gave the highest land equivalent ratio (Table 3). Compensation occurred in most cases, except in the IET2683 and IR42 combination where mutual cooperation existed. Mutual inhibition was observed with IR579 and IR42.

Yield advantages were not appreciable when maturity differences were less than 30 days. The correlation between grain

Table 1. Grain yield of sole-crop rice cultivars with different maturities in West Bengal, India.

Variety	Wet season		Dry season	
	Maturity (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Maturity (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)
CRM13	74	1.3	100	2.7
ET2683	100	3.1	120	5.6
IET1444	109	3.4	124	5.6
IR579	122	3.3	129	5.5
IR36	129	3.3	134	5.5
IR42	142	3.3	164	5.5

Table 2. Grain yield of intercropped rice cultivars of different maturities in West Bengal, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	Wet season		Dry season	
	Early variety	Late variety	Early variety	Late variety
CRM13 + IR36	0.6	2.7	1.3	3.3
CRM13 + IR42	0.6	2.8	1.3	3.6
IET2683 + IR36	2.0	1.6	2.9	2.3
IET2683 + IR42	1.9	2.5	3.5	2.7
IET1444 + IR36	2.0	2.0	3.3	2.4
IET1444 + IR42	1.8	2.3	3.4	2.6
IR579 + IR36	1.6	1.6	2.2	2.7
IR579 + IR42	1.5	2.0	2.8	2.5
IR36 + IR42	1.7	1.7	3.0	2.4
LSD (0.05)	0.63		0.59	

yield and differences in maturity of two varieties in mixture was 0.72 in the dry season and 0.88 in the wet. When the maturity difference was greater than 40 days, the yield advantage decreased, probably because of the low yield potential of very early-maturing CRM13.

Increased intercrop yields were associated with the formation of more panicles. High competitive abilities were

recorded in IR36 and IR42 in the wet season. In the dry season, IET2683 and IET1444 showed good competitive ability when they were cropped with a late-maturing variety.

Intraspecies intercropping yields were higher in the wet season than in the dry. These potential yield advantages will necessitate changes in harvesting practices. ■

Table 3. Land equivalent ratio and competitive ratio under variety intercropping combinations. West Bengal, India.

Treatment	Land equivalent ratio (LER) ^a						Competitive ratio (CR) ^b			
	Wet season			Dry season			Wet season		Dry season	
	Early variety	Late variety	Total variety	Early variety	Late variety	Total variety	Early variety	Late variety	Early variety	Late variety
CRM13 + IR36	0.46	0.82	1.28	0.56	0.60	1.16	0.56	1.78	0.93	1.07
CRM13 + IR42	0.46	0.85	1.34	0.48	0.64	1.12	0.52	1.85	0.75	1.33
IET2683 + IR36	0.65	0.48	1.11	0.52	0.41	0.93	0.53	0.74	1.27	0.79
IET2683 + IR42	0.63	0.76	1.39	0.62	0.49	1.11	1.35	0.68	1.26	0.79
ET1444 + IR36	0.53	0.70	1.23	0.59	0.43	1.02	0.80	1.32	1.38	0.73
ET1444 + IR42	0.59	0.70	1.29	0.60	0.47	1.07	0.84	1.19	1.28	0.78
IR579 + IR36	0.48	0.48	0.96	0.40	0.49	0.89	1.00	1.00	0.82	1.22
IR579 + IR42	0.45	0.61	1.06	0.50	0.45	0.95	0.75	1.35	0.67	0.90
IR36 + IR42	0.52	0.52	1.04	0.55	0.44	0.99	1.00	1.00	1.25	0.80

^aRelative area of sole crop required to produce intercropping yield. ^bCR of a = LER crop a/LER crop b, and CR of b = LER crop b/LER crop a.